

Leadership Influence Village Head toward Village Development in Pengaron District, Banjar Regency

Heni Susanti¹, Saudatul Munawaroh²
University of Achmad Yani Banjarmasin
^{1,2}Faculty of Administrative Science

Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine the extent of the influence of village head leadership on village development in the Pengaron District, Banjar Regency. This type of research is qualitative with field research methods. This is a method of collecting data by direct involvement in the field with the object of research being the Effect of Village Head Leadership on Village Development Results in the Pengaron District, Banjar Regency, South Kalimantan Province. Based on the results of the analysis and hypotheses previously stated, they can be maintained, because they are supported by data, the leadership of the village head has a very high influence on the results of village development in the study object village in the Pengaron sub-district.

Keywords:- Banjares, Leadership, village development, villagers.

I. INTRODUCTION

National development goals seek balance and harmony between urban areas and rural areas in order to reform rural areas. One of the efforts that the Republic of Indonesia wants to achieve in order to realize this goal is to carry out development, both spiritual area development and physical material development. Because the essence of Indonesia's national development is human development by the whole and development develops itself outwardly and inwardly consciously. Even though most of Indonesia's population lives in rural areas, it would be appropriate if development is directed primarily at rural development.

Development for the village itself is divided into two types, namely: the first non-physical development and the second physical development. Non-physical development basically prioritizes human resources, therefore non-physical development is shown to increase living standards and welfare in the long term both in the fields of education, health, as well as improving the rural economy. And while physical development or what is often referred to as village infrastructure development which includes the construction of village facilities and infrastructure, including the construction of irrigation, village bridges, village health infrastructure facilities, village markets and village roads. Physical village development is the construction of physical buildings that can be seen directly in the village or visible to the eye. [1].

In its implementation, the physical development of villages in the Pengaron District area which consists of 12 villages, namely: (1). Alimukim Village, (2). AntrakuVillage,(3). Ati'im Village, (4). Fort Village, (5). KertakEmpat Village, (6). New hole village, (7). Lok

Tunggul Village, (8). LumpangiVillage,(9). Mangkauk Village, (10). Maniapun Village, (11). PenyiuranVillage,(12). Pengaron Village.

However, in fact, the researchers saw in the 12 villages that there were still many village heads who were less than optimal in carrying out their duties and functions as a leader, seen from the lack of creativity, due to the lack of education. One of the problems in the village is the lack of synergy between fellow members of the AIT (Activity Implementation Team) and with village officials. So that in the implementation of village physical development, it is not in accordance with the previously established development plan. As a result, the quality of village physical development in the Pengaron District is less than optimal and far from previous expectations. Terry suggested that leadership of an activity influences others to work hard voluntarily for the benefit of the group [2]. Based on the opinion of George R Terry, it can be said that leadership lies in the ability and ability to influence others to act or act to achieve the goal of building their village towards a better direction by prioritizing the quality of physical development. While the village head is someone who has the highest position in the village government. As the head of the village government, he is fully responsible for the implementation of government, including in general government and fostering peace and order, development including physical and social development.

II. REVIEW OF THE ORIES AND PREVIOUS RESEARCH

The emergence of the notion of leader and leadership is since humans live in groups. Achmadi proposes a theory that humans have been created as social beings (Zoon Politicon) humans like to live in groups due to the urge of the human mind itself [3]. Tannenbaum argues that leadership is an attempt to influence other people in human relationships in a situation and is directed through communication processes to achieve the goals or objectives that have been set [4]. Tead argues that leadership is an activity to influence others to work together to achieve certain desired goals [5]. Arifin defines a leader as someone who can move other people around him (around him, under him in his influence) to follow the leader [6]. Based on the definition of the definition of a leader or leader, it can be known through the main elements of the notion of leader and leadership (Leader and Leadership), namely:

- The existence of a person's activeness and ability to influence people by guiding, directing and moving human behavior (leading and being led elements).
- The existence of the activeness and skills of one's person to hold or create various kinds of cooperation through the

correct and good communication process (for certain situations).

- There is cooperation and certain goals to be achieved by actively utilizing other people's energy (objective elements).

The qualities required for a leader are not the same in every society, although it is not uncommon for similarities to exist. Soeryono suggests *Astra Brata* or the eight attributes of a god that must be carried out by a king in ancient times, which in the Indonesian government system is known as a leader [7], as follows.

- *Indra Brata*, who gives pleasure in the physical field.
- *Yama Brata*, which refers to justice and legal certainty.
- *Surya Brata*, who moves his subordinates by inviting them to work persuasion.
- *CaciBrata*, which gives spiritual pleasure.
- *BayuBrata*, who demonstrates the toughness of education and does not hesitate to feel the difficulties of his followers.
- *Agni Brata*, which is the nature of giving encouragement to subordinates.

While the characteristics of leadership based on the opinion of Karyadi [8], are as follows.

- Decisiveness in making decisions, namely the ability and ability to quickly, decisively and precisely make this decision with dignity, conciseness and clarity.
- The ability to guide, evaluate and arrive at a conclusion. Before making a decision, we usually pay attention and weigh the various factors and materials that we have.
- Intelligence, what is meant by this trait is to face and solve problems with intelligence and ingenuity.
- Alertness and vigilance, alertness causes us to make decisions quickly and also the ability to know in advance, if this problem arises it needs to be accompanied by vigilance to prevent, at least reduce negligence, causing not to be rash and not hastily make decisions.
- Initiative and excitement, because a leader must initiate an action to move something. So he couldn't be indifferent. So even if there are no orders or instructions, you can't stay silent even though you know that something has to be done.
- A sense of responsibility, this is a deep and understanding sense of responsibility to not only be responsible for the work of the boss but more than that.
- Loyalty, this trait is also interpreted in the relationship of responsibility to duties, to superiors, but to subordinates, to the public we serve as community fire.
- Fair, impartial, objective, impartial, also in giving praise, reprimand and disciplinary action.
- Integrity, namely honesty and moral character which means above all doubts and reproaches.
- Humility, free from arrogance, pride, which is excessive, if the pride was not in its place.
- Wisdom, to get along and relate to superiors, subordinates, as well as colleagues and the community in a reasonable place, with an attitude that is quite correct without piercing feelings that cause anger or embarrassment to others.
- *Sepi ingpamrih*, which puts the public interest above the

interests of one's own and group means: Do not think about and benefit yourself by forgetting the public interest and harming others.

- Physical courage, especially for moral courage, means not only courage that is caused physically but because of the mind which is based on morals, courage, honesty.
- Sympathy, this is indeed a social need, a desire that exists in every human being who needs sympathy.
- Humor, this looks strange but is very helpful in real life practice. Humor does not mean that we ourselves are good at joking, but appreciate and see the benefits of events that are ridiculous and funny.

Village community development is generally carried out by all village officials with the direction of leaders and parties who have expertise in their fields. Siagian argues that community development is the process of rural communities accepting reform efforts in order to improve their standard of living [9]. Village development requires assistance from outside parties, in this case from the government through sent officers.

Village communities in general live in socio-economic conditions that still require attention due to lack of capital, low levels of education, lack of personnel who are less able to guide them towards renewal plus the heterogeneity that is quite high among village communities, but all of this must be accepted and used by officers as a whip to find a solution that will be used for efforts to build village communities.

Village communities are still obedient to hereditary traditions and customs, some of which can hinder and hinder development efforts due to deviations from traditions and customs. Especially for villages that are isolated from the outside world, most of the residents are very supportive of existing traditions and customs. Traditions and customs hold the villagers together. This feeling of interdependence causes them to adhere to shared norms, both in acting and behaving.

On the other hand, many villages have begun to be reached and are affected by its development. New values began to be imposed by the activities of the residents. The old balance or harmony insured the measure of values to act becomes erratic. The feeling of mutual attachment weakens, causing society to become divided or disintegrate. Disintegration in the community raises many problems which consequently make it very difficult for rural community development efforts.

Village community development efforts must pay attention to the environmental conditions of each village. This further complicates the tasks and work that can kill the spirit of the village community development officers. However, given that the village community is actually a community member who needs and must be considered and developed, the village community development efforts should not be ignored. All existing challenges must be used as a whip to work harder and more diligently. This is used as an impetus to think and act towards how to make life in the village have a brighter and more interesting perspective than life in the city for those who live in the village.

Suryadi explained several principles of success in developing rural communities [10]. The first principle is that officers must manifest friendship and trust with the people they will influence, meaning that officers practically feel living in the countryside for a certain period of time with the aim of observing and exploring existing problems. Officers must be friendly and kind and friendly so that their presence is well received by the community, so that it is easy for officers to invite them to discuss problems that are trying to solve them. Besides that, the officer must be aware that he is functioning, meaning "Working with" does not function "Working among" the community, therefore the officer does not impose his will and will, on the contrary he must learn about the village and must respect the prevailing customs. The second principle, officers, must obtain approval from the community regarding the development efforts to be carried out. Development plans or ideas must be communicated to the community in advance, either through local community leaders or other existing informal groups. The best way is actually holding discussions with the community and involving the community from thinking about the problems they face to making decisions about what to do for village development and their lives. The third principle, officers must show that the development efforts to be carried out do not endanger their interests. Most rural communities live in poverty, due to meager income. The new way of working is expected to increase their income, but because the new way of working has not yet shown tangible results, people find it difficult to accept it. Difficulty accepting the new way of working because they are afraid that a decrease in income will cause a decrease in job income. Scott put forward the concept of subsistence ethics, namely as a consequence of a life that is so close to the boundary line [11]. A decrease in income does not only mean less food, perhaps for the sake of eating he is forced to sacrifice his self-esteem or is forced to sell part of his livelihood so as to reduce the possibility of life for him to achieve adequate subsistence in the following days or years, which makes life fall further below the subsistence level, as a result the failure or reduced performance of a job is so high risk that for them it is better and often to use what is considered safe and reliable rather than profit.

The fourth principle is that officers should work with groups so that the ideas or ideas to be implemented can involve all members of the community. In fact, the discussions and decisions made by the group are mostly carried out. If there is no group in one village, the officers should encourage them to form a group. The formation of groups should be based on interests and things that already exist. Officers must always be aware that their function is only to serve and encourage the group and not to lead it. The function is to find what people want, to get them what they want to do.

Hermansyah, in the research entitled "The Influence of Village Head Leadership on the Implementation of Physical

Development in the Sidanglaya Village, Karangpawitan District, Garut Regency". The method used is descriptive method, the data is analyzed statistically using non-parametric statistical analysis using the Sperman Rank Correlation Coefficient approach. The results of the study stated that the leadership of the village head of Sidanglayais good, it's just that the community still does not understand the importance of community self-help to build a quality physical village of Sidanglaya. Kumalasari in her research entitled "Leadership of the Ciamis Village Head in Village Development in Ciamis Village, North Sungkai District, North Lampung Regency", with a qualitative method with analysis techniques using data reduction, data display, and drawing conclusions. The conclusion of the research is that it focuses on the situational leadership style of delegation. This is indicated by low support and low direction from the village head, and on the other hand followers are unable and unwilling to follow the orders and directions of their leaders, and village development factors that do not work such as bridges, culverts, gutters, street lights The Development Index in Ciamis Village is small and results in Ciamis Village being a very underdeveloped village.

III. HYPOTHESIS

Based on the theory and the results of previous studies, the hypotheses of this study are as follows.

- H1: If the Village Head carries out his leadership well, then the impact on the results of village development is also good
- H2: If the village head does not carry out his leadership well, then the effect on the results of village development is not good

IV. METHODS

The type of research used in this study is a quantitative research method used to examine a particular population or sample, which data collection uses research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, which aims to test the established hypothesis. Field research (field research), aims to study intensively about the background of the current situation with the environmental interactions of a social unit both from individuals, groups, and institutions, as well as the community.

This field research is a method of collecting data by going directly to the field with the object of research being the Effect of Village Head Leadership on Village Development Results in the Pengaron District, Banjar Regency, South Kalimantan Province. The variables in this study are:

- Variable X (Independent Variable) is the leadership of the village head.
- Variable Y (Dependent Variable) is the result of village physical development.

variable	Operational definition	Indicator	Scale
independent Village Head Leadership	Creativity	1. Frequency of LPMD Meetings for the preparation of physical development plans 2. The presence of the Village Head at the LPMD meeting for the preparation of a physical development plan 3. Frequency of BPD Meetings 4. The presence of the village head in the BPD briefing meeting for the preparation of the village physical development plan 5. Number of physical development plans submitted by village heads that are approved by the BPD	Likert
	Briefing Meeting	1. Frequency of Village Apparatus briefing meetings 2. The presence of the village head in the village apparatus briefing meeting 3. Frequency of LPMD briefing meetings 4. The presence of the village head at the LPMD briefing meeting	Likert
	Counseling	1. Frequency of village community outreach 2. The presence of the village head in the village apparatus briefing meeting	Likert
	Motivation	1. Frequency of gotong royong activities 2. The presence of the village head in mutual cooperation activities	Likert
	review	1. Frequency of reviewing physical development in the field 2. Frequency of inspection	Likert
Depending on the Results of Village Physical Development	Number of Buildings	Number of buildings built	Likert
	Building Quality	1. Quality of the building built. 2. A lot of development costs	Likert
	Completion Time	Length of Completion	Likert

Table 1: Variables, Operational Definitions and Research Indicators

To find out the correlation between the two variables, a correlation calculation was carried out using the Sperman Rho formula.

$$Rho_{xy} = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

Description

- Rho = Correlation coefficient
- x = Independent Variable
- y = Dependent Variable
- d = The difference between levels
- N = Sample

Meanwhile, to determine the level of correlation used the following measures:

Correlation coefficient	Interpretation
0,90 – 1,00	Very High
0,70 – 0,90	High
0,40 – 0,70	Moderat
0,20 – 0,40	Lower
0,00 – 0,20	Very Low

Table 2: Correlation Coefficient Interpretation

To test whether the correlation coefficient obtained will be significant or not, a significance test was carried out using the Sperman Rho critical value guideline which determined that the critical price at N = 6 at the 95% confidence level was 0.886.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Overview of Research Sites

Astronomically, Pengaron District is located at 309°34"-3017'58" east longitude and 11507'50" - 11505'43" longitude.

Geographically, it is bordered by:

- To the north it is bordered by the Subdistrict of Connect
- To the east it is bordered by Sungai Pinang District.
- To the south, it is bordered by Karang Intan District.
- In the west with SimpangEmpat District.

Picture 1: Pengaron District Map

Source: Pengaron District Office, 2020

The area of Pengaron District reaches 433.25 Km² which is divided into 12 villages (twelve) villages. The following are the names of the villages and the area of the village in Pengaron District, as well as the distance between the village office and the government center in the District.

B. Demographic/Population Situation

Based on the 2019 Population Registration, Pengaron District has a population of 16,061 people with 8,212 men and 7,849 women.

The village with the most population is Mangkauk Village with a population of 3683 people. And the village with the least population is Lumpangi Village with 393 people.

To find out the relationship between the leadership level of the village head and the level of village physical development results, the researchers calculated the correlation of the two variables studied. It was hoped that the hypothesis could be tested. More details can be followed in the following discussion.

C. Village Head Leadership Level

• Creativity Level

- Frequency of Village Community Empowerment Institutions (LPMD) Meetings for Preparation of Development Plans.

No	Village	LPMD Meeting Frequency/Year	Score
1	Benteng	2	2
2	Pengaron	2	2
3	Maniapun	3	3
4	Lok Tunggul	2	2
5	Antaraku	3	3
6	Ati'im	2	2
N = 6		Total Score	14

Table 10: Level of Frequency of LPMD Meetings of Sudi Objects for the Preparation of Village Physical Development Plans for the Year 2019/2020

Source: Processed Research Results, 2020

Based on the analysis of the data presented in table 10 above, it can be argued that the frequency level of meetings of the Village Community Empowerment Institution (LPMD) for the preparation of development plans in 2019/2020 is considered more than sufficient.

- The Level of Attendance of Village Heads in the Meeting of Village Community Empowerment Institutions (LPMD) for the Preparation of Village Physical Development Plans. Regarding the level of presence of the village head in the meeting of the Village Community Empowerment Institute (LPMD) the object of study for the preparation of development plans can be followed in the following table.

No	Village	The Presence of Village-Style Kep that Should Be	Village Head Attendance Rate (%)	Score
1	Benteng	2 : 2	100	3
2	Pengaron	2 : 2	100	3
3	Maniapun	3 : 3	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	2 : 2	100	3
5	Antaraku	3 : 3	100	3
6	Ati'im	2 : 2	100	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 11: Attendance Rate of Village Head Object of Study Dalam LPMD Meeting for the Preparation of Development Plans for 2019/2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Based on the analysis of the data presented in table 11 above, it can be stated that the level of attendance of the village head in the meeting of the Village Community

Empowerment Institution (LPMD) for the preparation of development plans is considered good.

➤ Level of Meeting Frequency of Village Consultative Body (BPD)

No	Village	BPD Meeting Frequency/Year	Score
1	Benteng	3	3
2	Pengaron	3	3
3	Maniapun	3	3
4	Lok Tunggul	2	2
5	Antaraku	3	3
6	Ati'im	2	2
N = 6		Total Score	16

Table 12: Frequency Level of BPD Meetings for Study Objects for the Preparation of Development Plans for 2019/2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Based on the data presented in table 12 of the frequency of the Village Consultative Body (BPD) Meeting, the object of study for the preparation of development plans in 2019/2020 is considered more than sufficient.

➤ The Level of Attendance of Village Heads in village consultative body (BPD) meetings

No	Village	The presence of the Village Head is as Real as it is present	Village Head Attendance Rate (%)	Score
1	Benteng	3 : 3	100	3
2	Pengaron	3 : 3	100	3
3	Maniapun	3 : 3	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	2 : 2	100	3
5	Antaraku	3 : 3	100	3
6	Ati'im	2 : 2	100	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 13: The Level of Attendance of the Head of the Study Object Village in the BPD Meeting for the Preparation of Development Plans for 2019 to 2020

Source: Processed Research Results, 2020

From the analysis of the data presented in table 13, it is stated that the level of attendance of the Village Head of the object of study in the village consultative body (BPD) meeting for the preparation of development plans in 2019/2020 can be considered good.

➤ *The Level of The Number of Development Plans submitted by the Village Head approved by the Village Consultative Body (BPD)*

No	Village	Number of Proposed Developments That Are Approved	Approved Development (%)	Score
1	Benteng	7 : 7	100	3
2	Pengaron	7 : 7	100	3
3	Maniapun	5 : 5	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	7 : 7	100	3
5	Antaraku	6 : 6	100	3
6	Ati'im	6 : 6	100	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 14: Level of Number of Physical Development Plans Approved by BPD Object of Study 2019/2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Based on the data presented in table 14, the number of development plans submitted by the village head approved by the Village Consultative Body (BPD) in the 2019/2020 study object can be considered good.

After the data is analyzed and interpreted, the following can be studied the level of creativity of the village head of the object of study. For this reason, it can be followed by the calculations presented in table 15 below.

No	Village	Village Head's Creativity Level					Total Score	Mean Score
		A	B	C	D	E		
1	Benteng	2	3	3	3	3	14	2,8
2	Pengaron	2	3	3	3	3	14	2,8
3	Maniapun	3	3	3	3	3	15	3
4	Lok Tunggul	2	3	2	3	3	13	2,6
5	Antaraku	3	3	3	3	3	15	3
6	Ati'im	2	3	2	3	3	13	2,6
N = 6		Total Score						16,8

Table 15: Village Head's Creativity Level

Source: Processed Data , 2020.

Description:

LPMD Frequency Meeting Level for Development Plan Preparation.

- a. Village Head Attendance Rate in LPMD Meeting.
- b. Tingkat FrekuensiRapat BPD.
- c. Village Head Attendance Rate in BPD Meeting.
- d. The Level of The Number of Development Plans

D. Level of Organizing Briefing Meetings.

- *Frequency Level of Village Apparatus Briefing Meetings.*

Submitted by the Village Head Approved by BPD.

From the calculations presented in table 15 above, it is understandable that the level of creativity of the village head of the object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be assessed on average close to good.

No	Village	Frequency of Village Apparatus Briefing Meetings per Year	Score
1	Benteng	11	2
2	Pengaron	11	2
3	Maniapun	12	3
4	Lok Tunggul	12	3
5	Antaraku	12	3
6	Ati'im	12	3
N = 6		Total Score	16

Table 16: Frequency Level of Village Apparatus Briefing Meetings on Study Objects from 2019 to 2020

Source: Processed Data , 2020

Based on the analysis of data presented in table 16 above, it can be stated that the level of frequency of briefing

meetings of village officials of the object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be considered more than sufficient.

➤ *The Level of Attendance of village heads in the village apparatus briefing meeting.*

No	Village	The Presence of the Village Head as Real as Possible	Village Head Presence Rate (x)	Score
1	Benteng	10 : 11	91	3
2	Pengaron	9 : 11	82	3
3	Maniapun	12 : 12	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	10 : 12	83	3
5	Antaraku	12 : 12	100	3
6	Ati'im	12 : 12	100	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 17: The Level of Attendance of the Village Head of the Object of Study in the 2019/2020 Village Apparatus Briefing Meeting

Source: Data Processed, 2020

From the results of the data analysis presented in table 17, it is stated that the level of attendance of the village head of the object of study in the 2019/2020 village apparatus briefing meeting is considered good.

➤ *Frequency Level of Briefing Meetings of Village Community Empowerment Institutions (LPMD)*

No	Village	Frequency of LPMD Briefing Meetings / Year	Score
1	Benteng	5	1
2	Pengaron	5	1
3	Maniapun	12	3
4	Lok Tunggul	11	2
5	Antaraku	12	3
6	Ati'im	11	2
N = 6		Total Score	12

Table 18: Frequency Level of LPMD Briefing Meetings object of study 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

From the analysis of the data presented in table 18, it is stated that the level of frequency of briefing meetings of the Village Community Empowerment Institute (LPMD) of the object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be considered sufficient.

➤ *The Level of Attendance of Village Heads in the Briefing Meeting of the Village Community Empowerment Institute (LPMD)*

No	Village	The Presence of the Village Head as Real as Possible	Village Head Attendance Rate (x)	Score
1	Benteng	5 : 5	100	3
2	Pengaron	5 : 5	100	3
3	Maniapun	12 : 12	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	10 : 12	83	3
5	Antaraku	12 : 12	100	3
6	Ati'im	12 : 12	100	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 19: The Level of Attendance of the Head of the Village Object of Study in the LPMD Briefing Meeting from 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

From the results of the data analysis presented in table 20, it can be stated that the level of attendance of the village head of the object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be considered good.

following is studied the level of organizing a briefing meeting by the village head of the object of study, which can be followed by the calculations presented in table 21 below.

After the data is analyzed and interpreted, the

No	Village	Level of Organizing Briefing Meetings				Total Score	Mean Score
		A	B	C	D		
1	Benteng	2	3	1	3	9	2,5
2	Pengaron	2	3	1	3	9	2,5
3	Maniapun	3	3	3	3	12	3
4	Lok Tunggul	3	3	2	3	11	2,7
5	Antaraku	3	3	3	3	12	3
6	Ati'im	3	3	2	3	11	2,7
N = 6		Total Score					16,4

Table 21: Level of Organizing Briefing Meetings from 2019 to 2020

Source: Processed Data, 2020

Information:

- Frequency Level of Village Apparatus Briefing Meetings.
- The Level of Attendance of the Village Head of the Object of Study in the Village Apparatus Briefing Meeting
- Lpmd Briefing Meeting Frequency Level.
- The Level of Attendance of the Head of the Village Object

of Study in the LPMD Briefing Meeting.

- From the calculations presented in table 21, it is understandable that the level of holding the briefing meeting conducted by the head of the village object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be assessed on average close to good.

E. Level of Counseling

➤ *Tingkat PenyuluhanWargaDesa.*

No	Village	Frequency of Counseling for Villagers / Year	Score
1	Benteng	11	2
2	Pengaron	11	2
3	Maniapun	12	3
4	Lok Tunggul	11	2
5	Antaraku	12	3
6	Ati'im	11	2
N = 6		Total Score	14

Table 22: Level of Frequency of Village Counseling from 2019 to 2020

Source: Processed Data, 2020

From the description of the data presented in table 43 above, it can be argued that the level of frequency of

counseling for villagers of the object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be assessed as more than sufficient.

➤ *The Level of Presence of Village Heads in Counseling Villagers.*

No	Village	The Presence of the Village Head as Real as Possible	Village Head Attendance Rate (x)	Score
1	Benteng	10 : 11	91	3
2	Pengaron	10 : 11	91	3
3	Maniapun	12 : 12	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	10 : 11	91	3
5	Antaraku	12 : 12	100	3
6	Ati'im	11 : 12	92	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 23: The Level of Attendance of The Village Head of the Object of Study in the Counseling of Villagers in 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Based on the analysis of data presented in table 23, the attendance rate of village heads from 2019 to 2020 can be considered good.

After the data is analyzed and interpreted, the following will be studied the level of counseling of the villagers of the object of study. For this reason, the calculations presented in table 24 below can be followed.

No	Village	Village Community Counseling Level		Total Score	Mean Score
		A	B		
1	Benteng	2	3	5	2,5
2	Pengaron	2	3	5	2,5
3	Maniapun	3	3	6	3
4	Lok Tunggul	2	3	5	2,5
5	Antaraku	3	3	6	3
6	Ati'im	2	3	5	2,5
N = 6		Total Score		16	

Table 24: Level of Counseling for Villagers object of study 2019 to 2020

Source: Processed Data , 2020.

Description:

A= Level of Counseling for Villagers.

B= The Level of Attendance of the Village Head in Counseling.

From the calculations presented in table 24, it can be stated that the level of counseling of villagers from the object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be assessed as more than sufficient.

F. Motivation Level

- Level of Frequency of Mutual Aid Activities.

No	Village	Frequency of Mutual Aid Activities / Year	Score
1	Benteng	11	2
2	Pengaron	11	2
3	Maniapun	12	3
4	Lok Tunggul	12	3
5	Antaraku	12	3
6	Ati'im	12	3
N = 6		Total Score	16

Table 25: Frequency Level of Mutual Cooperation of Village Object of Study 2019 to 2020

Source: Processed Data, 2020.

Based on the analysis of the data presented in table 25 above, it can be stated that the frequency level mutual aid

activities in the study objects from 2019 to 2020 can be assessed on average more than enough.

- The Level of Presence of Village Heads in Mutual Aid Activities.

No	Village	The Presence of the Village Head as Real as Possible	Village Head Attendance Rate (x)	Score
1	Benteng	11 : 11	100	3
2	Pengaron	11 : 11	100	3
3	Maniapun	12 : 12	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	12 : 12	100	3
5	Antaraku	12 : 12	100	3
6	Ati'im	12 : 12	100	3
N = 6		Total Score	18	

Table 26: The Level of Presence of Village Heads in Mutual Cooperation Activities from 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

From the analysis of the data presented in table 26 above, it can be stated that the level of attendance of the village head of the object of study in 2019/2020 can be considered good.

After the data is analyzed and interpreted, the following is studied the level of motivation carried out by the village head of the object of study. For that can be followed the calculations presented in table 48 below.

No	Village	Motivation Level		Total Score	Mean Score
		A	B		
1	Benteng	2	3	5	2,5
2	Pengaron	2	3	5	2,5
3	Maniapun	3	3	6	3
4	Lok Tunggul	3	3	6	3
5	Antaraku	3	3	6	3
6	Ati'im	3	3	6	3
N = 6		Total Score		17	

Table 27: The Level of Motivation Carried Out by the Village Head in 2019 to 2020

Source: Processed Data , 2020.

Information:

A= Frequency Level of Mutual Aid Activities.
 B= The Level of Presence of Village Heads in Mutual Aid Activities.

From the calculations presented in table 48 above, it can be argued that the level of motivation carried out by the village head of the study object in 2019 to 2020 can be considered close to good.

G. Review Rate

- Frequency of Physical Development Review in the Field.

No	Village	Frequency of Review of Physical Buildings / Years	Score
1	Benteng	11	2
2	Pengaron	11	2
3	Maniapun	12	3
4	Lok Tunggul	11	2
5	Antaraku	12	3
6	Ati'im	12	3
N = 6		Total Score	15

Table 28: Frequency Level of Review of Physical Buildings in the field in 2019/2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020.

Based on the analysis of the data mentioned above in table 28, it can be stated that the frequency level of review of

physical buildings in the field of the village object of study in 2019/2020 is considered on average more than sufficient.

- Frequency Level of Financial Administration Examinations.

No	Village	Frequency of Review of Physical Buildings / Years	Score
1	Benteng	11	2
2	Pengaron	12	3
3	Maniapun	12	3
4	Lok Tunggul	12	3
5	Antaraku	12	3
6	Ati'im	12	3
N = 6		Total Score	17

Table 29: Frequency Level of Financial Administration Examinations in 2019/2020

Source: Processed Data , 2020

Based on the data presented in table 29 above, it can be argued that the level of frequency of village financial administration examinations of the object of study in 2019/2020 can be assessed on average close to good.

After the data is analyzed and interpreted, the following is studied the level of review carried out by the village head of the object of study. For this reason, the calculations presented in table 30 below can be followed.

No	Village	Review Rate		Total Score	Mean Score
		A	B		
1	Benteng	2	2	4	2
2	Pengaron	3	3	6	3
3	Maniapun	3	3	6	3
4	Lok Tunggul	3	3	6	3
5	Antaraku	3	3	6	3
6	Ati'im	3	3	6	3
N = 6		Total Score		17	

Table 30: Level of Review Conducted by Village Heads from 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020.

Information:

A = Frequency Level of Physical Building Review.

B = Frequency Level of Financial Administration Examinations.

From the calculations presented in table 30 above, it can be argued that the level of review carried out by the

village head of the object of study in 2019 to 2020 can be considered close to good.

After all the village head leadership data is analyzed and interpreted, it can be studied the level of leadership of the village head object of study. For this reason, it can be studied in table 31 below.

No	Village	Leadership Level					Total	Mean
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	Benteng	2,8	2,5	2,5	2,5	2	12	2,4
2	Pengaron	2,8	2,5	2,5	2,5	3	12	2,4
3	Maniapun	3	3	3	3	3	15	3
4	Lok Tunggul	2,6	2,7	2,5	3	3	13,8	2,7
5	Antaraku	3	3	3	3	3	15	3
6	Ati'im	2,6	2,7	2,5	3	3	13,8	2,7
N = 6		Total Score					16,2	

Table 31: Village Head Leadership Level 2019/2020

Source: Processed Data , 2020.

Description:

- Level of Creativity.
- Level of Briefing Meeting.
- Level of Counseling.
- Motivation Level
- Review Level.

Based on the calculation results presented in table 52 above, it can be stated that the level of Leadership of the Head of the Village Object of Study in 2019/2020 can be considered close to good.

H. Village Physical Development Outcome Level

- Level number of buildings.

No	Village	Number of Buildings built / Number of planned	Level of Number of Buildings built(%)	Score
1	Benteng	4 : 7	57	1
2	Pengaron	5 : 7	71	2
3	Maniapun	5 : 5	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	5 : 7	71	2
5	Antaraku	5 : 6	83	3
6	Ati'im	4 : 6	66	2
N = 6		Total Score		13

Table 32: The Level of the Number of Buildings Built in 2019/2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

From the analysis of the data presented in table 32 above, it can be argued that the level of the number of buildings that can be built in the village of the object of

study in 2019 to 2020 can be assessed as more than sufficient.

➤ *Build Quality Level.*

No	Village	Number of Bangu built according to standards/Number of buildings built	Standard-compliant level of built buildings(%)	Score
1	Benteng	4 : 4	100	3
2	Pengaron	5 : 5	100	3
3	Maniapun	5 : 5	100	3
4	Lok Tunggul	5 : 5	100	3
5	Antaraku	5 : 5	100	3
6	Ati'im	4 : 4	100	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 33: Quality Level of Buildings Built from 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

From the analysis of the data presented in table 33, it can be stated that the level of quality established in 2019 to 2020 is considered on average good.

➤ *Development Cost Level*

No	Desa	the amount of the Cost of Buildings from the Village Fund / The total amount (Rp)	The Rate of Cost from the Village Fund(%)	Score
1	Benteng	645.000.000 : 933.000.000	69	2
2	Pengaron	612.000.000 : 933.000.000	65	2
3	Maniapun	675.000.000 : 933.000.000	72	2
4	Lok Tunggul	565.000.000 : 933.000.000	60	2
5	Antaraku	630.000.000 : 933.000.000	67	2
6	Ati'im	585.000.000 : 933.000.000	62	2
N = 6		Total Score		12

Table 34: Cost Level of Construction of Physical Buildings in 2019/2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Based on the analysis of the data presented in table 34 mentioned above, presumably it can be argued that the level of cost of building physical buildings of the village object of study in 2019 to 2020 is considered sufficient.

➤ *Development Completion Time Level.*

No	Village	Village	Number of Buildings that can be completed in the right time	Score
1	Benteng	4	4	3
2	Pengaron	5	5	3
3	Maniapun	5	5	3
4	Lok Tunggul	5	5	3
5	Antaraku	5	5	3
6	Ati'im	4	4	3
N = 6		Total Score		18

Table 35: Completion Time Level of Physical Buildings from 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Based on the analysis presented in table 35, it can be stated that the level of the number of buildings that can be completed in the established time can be assessed as good.

After all data from the results of the physical development of the village object of study are analyzed and interpreted, it can be studied the level of physical development results of the village object of study presented in table 36 below.

No	Village	Village Physical Development Outcome Level				Total	Mean
		A	B	C	D		
1	Benteng	1	3	2	3	9	2,2
2	Pengaron	2	3	2	3	10	2,5
3	Maniapun	3	3	2	3	11	2,7
4	Lok Tunggul	2	3	2	3	10	2,5
5	Antaraku	3	3	2	3	11	2,7
6	Ati'im	2	3	2	3	10	2,5
N = 6		Total Score					15,1

Table 36: Level of Physical Development Results from 2019 to 2020

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Description:

- A = Number of Buildings
- B = Quality Level of Buildings That Have Been Built
- C = Building Cost Rate.
- D = Building Completion Time Level.

Based on the calculations that have been carried out in table 36 above, it can be stated that the level of physical development results of the village object of study from 2019 to 2020 can be assessed on average more than sufficient.

➤ The Correlation Level of Village Head Leadership with Village Physical Development Results. After the data of the Village Head's Leadership and the Results of The Physical Development of the Village Object of Study are analyzed and interpreted, the following will be presented calculation of the correlation of the two variables.

In this connection, the Rho Sperman Formula will be used, namely:

$$Rho_{xy} = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

Regarding the presence or absence of the relationship of the two variables can be followed the calculations presented in table 37 below.

No	Village	X	Y	Rx	Ry	D	d ²
1	Benteng	2,4	2,2	5,5	5	0,5	0,25
2	Pengaron	2,4	2,5	5,5	4	1,5	2,25
3	Maniapun	3	2,7	1,5	1,5	0	0
4	Lok Tunggul	2,7	2,5	3,5	4	-0,5	0,25
5	Antaraku	3	2,7	1,5	1,5	0	0
6	Ati'im	2,7	2,5	3,5	4	-0,5	0,25
N = 6						d ² = 3	

Table 37: Calculation of the Correlation of Village Head Leadership with Village Physical Development Results

Source: Processed Data, 2020.

$$Rho_{xy} = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

$$= 1 - \frac{6 \times 3}{6(36 - 1)} = 1 - \frac{18}{210} = 1 - 0,085 = 0,915$$

From the results of the correlation calculation, a correlation coefficient of 0.915 was obtained. While the price of criticism from the correlation coefficient according to Sperman Rho for N = 6 at the level of 95% confidence is 0.886, then thus that leadership has a high influence on village development.

VI. CONCLUSIONS, IMPLICATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Dotted with the results of the analysis and data interplay then continued with the calculation of the correlation of free variables and dependent variables as presented in front. If the correlation coefficient of the two variables is higher than the price of criticism, then the hypothesis is up front of being maintained. Similarly, if the correlation coefficient is lower than the price of criticism set, the hypothesis cannot be maintained.

In this connection, based on the critique price of the correlation coefficient according to Sperman for n = 6 at the level of 95% confidence is 0.886 while the correlation coefficient of the two variables namely Village Head Leadership and Village Development Results exceeds the set criticism price of 0.915, thus that the correlation coefficient mentioned above is significant because it is

higher than the price of criticism.

The provisional answer said "If the Village Head carries out his Leadership well, then the influence on the results of village development is also good. And vice versa". Based on the hypothesis stated earlier, it can be maintained, because it is supported by data or in other words, the Leadership of the Village Head has a very high effect on the results of Village Development in the Object of Study Village in the Region Kecamatan Pengaron.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Kuncoro, Mudrajad, *Otonomi dan Pembangunan Daerah*. Jakarta: Fokusmedia, 2010.
- [2.] Terry, George R, *Prinsip-prinsip Manajemen*, Penerjemah J-Smith D.F.M. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara, 2012.
- [3.] Achmadi, Abu. *Psikologi Sosial*. Surabaya: Bina Ilmu, TT
- [4.] Tannenbaum, Robert and Warren H. Schmidt. *Managers as Leaders*. USA: A Harvard Business Review Paperback. 1990.
- [5.] Ordway Tead, *The Art of Leadership*. New York: McGraw Hill Book Company. 1960.
- [6.] Arifin, Abdurachman. *Teori Pembangunan dan Filosofi Kepemimpinan Kerja*. Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan Nasional, 2002
- [7.] Soeryono, Soekanto. *Sosiologi Suatu Pengantar*. Jakarta: Yayasan Penerbit Universitas Indonesia. 1997.
- [8.] Karyadi, Moch. *Kepemimpinan*. Bandung: PT. Karya Nusantara, 1977.
- [9.] Siagin, H. *Pokok-pokok Pembangunan Masyarakat Desa*. Bandung: Alumni. 1983.
- [10.] Suryadi, A. *Pembangunan Masyarakat Desa*. Bandung : PT Alumni. 1988.
- [11.] Scoot, James C. *Moral Ekonomi Petani, Pergolakan dan Subsistensi di Asia Tenggara*. Jakarta: LP3ES (Lembaga Penelitian, Pendidikan dan Penerangan Ekonomi dan Sosial).